

Solution stability and thermal degradation of some cyclic dithiocarbamates

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Abstract : Although cyclic dithiocarbamates (DTC) present better solution and solid state stability when compared to aliphatic analogues, relatively few thermo-analytical and solution stability studies have so far been reported which concern these important substances. In solution, the degradation of dithiocarbamates undergoes via a protonated intermediate and is very fast in acidic media. A spectrophotometric method based on diode array detection has been proposed for a fast and accurate determination of pK_a and degradation kinetic constants of these cyclic DTC's and is discussed here. Thermal analytical data were also collected regarding ammonium, sodium, potassium salts as well as for zinc, cadmium, lead, cobalt, nickel, copper, mercury, silver, iron and manganese complexes of pyrrolidinedithiocarbamate (pyr), piperidinedithiocarbamate (pip), morpholinedithiocarbamate (mor) and hexamethylenimine dithiocarbamate (hex) and are summarized in this article. Differences in the decomposition intermediates permitted to conclude that structural differences make the decomposition to occur by specific pathways, depending on the number and nature of members of the aminic ring.

Keywords : Dithiocarbamates, solution stability, thermal analysis, pK_a .

I. Introduction

The dithiocarbamates (DTC) are the products of the reaction between a primary or secondary amine (aliphatic or aromatic) with carbon disulphide. The general formula of the salts formed is $[(H_2NR'R'')(R'R''N-CSS)]$, in which R' and R'' represent equal or different aliphatic chains or a cyclic amine¹. The corresponding ammonium or alkali metal salts can be obtained using the ammonium or the proper alkali hydroxide as proton acceptor respectively. The free acidic forms of the DTC are unstable in aqueous solution and few had been already isolated². The dithiocarbamates has also a remarked ability in complexing metal ions due to the -CSS group. The DTC salts and complexes are widely used in many different areas such as medicine, industry, agriculture and chemistry. Their properties and applications have been extensively discussed in many review articles²⁻¹⁰. It is easy to note that in such applications these compounds are submitted to diverse conditions in which they can undergo thermal or solution decomposition. In this sense the knowledge of thermal and solution stability properties can be an important tool

in order to guide the use of the DTC and its derivatives through the diverse range of applications. The information on the decomposition products can also be important in knowing what kind of residues can be released in the environment, living organisms and goods, involved respectively in agricultural, medical and industrial applications, as examples. The interest in the stability of DTC has been renewed by the utilization of such compounds as coadjuvants in the treatment of AIDS^{11,12}. They have also been suggested for tuberculosis¹³ and cancer¹⁴ treatment in the past. In these applications the compound must have enough chemical stability for an effective action in the biological medium. It is also known that cyclic derivatives use to be more thermally and chemically stable than the aliphatic ones⁹. In three of the reviews cited above, concerning the thermal behavior of DTC compounds³⁻⁵ most of references are related with the diethyldithiocarbamate thermal behavior. Few studies, however has been presented in relation to the cyclic DTC, such as pyrrolidinedithiocarbamate (pyr), piperidinedithiocarbamate (pip), morpholinedithiocarbamate (mor) and

hexamethylenedithiocarbamate (hex), whose structural formulae are :

Pyrrolidinedithiocarbamate is a versatile compound and is widely used, in solvent extraction and other analytical procedures, because of their resistance to acid media¹⁵. The Zn and Cd complexes with pip are applied in rubber

processing as curing agents¹⁶ and in photographic films^{17,18}. Fernandez-Alba *et al.*¹⁹, reported studies on the thermal decomposition of NH₄pyr and other DTC, with agricultural applications. Vibrational Spectroscopy was used to propose a structure to the solids. Diaz *et al.*²⁰ have studied decomposition fragments in mass spectroscopy for Bi, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Ni, Pb, Sb, Zn and ammonium in pyr compounds. Gomišček *et al.*²¹, presented X-ray diffraction studies for the characterisation of decomposition products of several pyr complexes with divalent cations. The decomposition products were obtained in 80, 150, 250, 300, 400 and 600 °C, under oxygen and argon atmospheres. The same authors²² reported the thermal behavior of Cd, Co, Cu, Fe, Ni, Pb and V - pyr complexes in graphite tubes for atomic absorption. Sceney *et al.*²³ studied the thermal decomposition of seven copper(II) dithiocarbamates by thermogravimetry under air and nitrogen atmospheres. Complete TG and DTA studies are reported to copper(II)-diethyldithiocarbamate complex under air, vacuum and nitrogen.

Thermal analysis of mixed nickel hexamethylenedithiocarbamate complexes with triphenyl and tributylphos-

phine²⁴ as well as for of lanthanides complexes with hexamethylenedithiocarbamate^{25,26} have been described. Recently the thermal behavior of the ammonium and hexamethyleneammonium salts of hexamethylenedithiocarbamate as well as some metallic complexes was also reported^{27,28}. Few reports on the behavior and/or characterization of pip and mor can be found.

II. Stability in aqueous solutions

The low stability of the DTC in acidic media has been pointed like the major limitation to the use of these versatile compounds. Zahradnick and Zuman²⁹ first reported studies concerning the decomposition reaction, and Chakrabarti and co-workers^{15,30-33} proposed a degradation mechanism related with the acidic form, represented by an unstable intermediate and generating an amine and carbon disulfide, according with the reaction :

These authors proposed that the instability of the intermediate, whose structure is presented in the Fig. 1, is due to the positive charge density in the carbon and nitrogen atoms of the carbamate bond (N-C), that induces the

Fig. 1. Acid decomposition intermediate, according to Joris *et al.*³¹.

molecule decomposition in acidic media. Thus the pK_a value for the DTC is an important feature since it is related with the compound stability and varies with the amminic substituent. However its determination is a problem due to the instability of the acidic form^{9,33}. The kinetic, polarographic or mathematical methods, proposed for the pK_a measurements³⁰⁻³³ are time consuming. Conventional potentiometric and spectrophotometric methods are not applicable because the rapid decomposition that occurs in acidic media. The development of a relatively single spectrophotometric method based on the Vogel's propose³⁴, but employing a diode-array spectrophotometer, whose speed of reading permits the data acquisition

in a so short time, that by-passes the compounds decomposition problem, has been described³⁵. The method was applied in the determination pK_a value of the pyrrolidinedithiocarbamic (Hpyr), piperidinedithiocarbamic (Hpip), morpholinedithiocarbamic (Hmor) and hexamethylenedithiocarbamic (Hhex) acids.

11.1. Molar absorptivity (ϵ) determination

According to Shakaranarayana and Patel³⁶, three absorption bands can be observed in the UV-vis spectra of dithiocarbamates. According to these authors the first band at lower wavelengths (350–360 nm) is related to the excitation of free electrons of sulphur atom to anti-bonding orbitals: $n \rightarrow \pi^*$. The second is attributed to transitions of the type $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ at N–C=S group, appearing at 250–260 nm. The last one typically at 280 nm belongs to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ in the S–C=S group. For the acidic form only one band is observed with maximum at 265–270 nm¹⁵, due to the protonation, that reduces the resonance in the N–CS₂ group. In the investigation of the solution stability and pK_a with such procedure first involves the determination of the molar absorptivity (ϵ) from angular coefficients of the absorbance vs molar concentration (mol L⁻¹) curves for the acidic and basic forms of each DTC, in the maximum wavelength (λ_{max}) region of both forms. The ϵ values are of the 10⁴ mol⁻¹ L cm⁻¹ order, according to the findings of Shankaranarayana and Patel³⁶. Typical results obtained for the cyclic DTC are represented in Table 1^{34,36,37}. They were measured from graphs as those presented in Fig. 1 for NH₄pyr as a representative example³⁵.

Table 1. Molar absorptivities, ϵ , determined for each DTC to both acid and basic forms

Compd.	pH	λ (nm)	ϵ (L mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	log ϵ
Hpyr	0.89	272	1.19 × 10 ⁴	4.1
pyr ⁻	7.82	256	1.45 × 10 ⁴	4.2
Hpip	0.89	276	5.26 × 10 ³	3.7
pip ⁻	7.82	264	1.45 × 10 ⁴	4.2
Hmor	1.23	264	2.14 × 10 ³	3.3
mor ⁻	7.61	286	2.06 × 10 ³	3.3
Hhex	1.23	260	1.22 × 10 ⁴	4.1
hex ⁻	7.61	276	1.06 × 10 ⁴	4.0

11.2. pK_a calculations

Once having the ϵ values they can be substituted in the equations system³⁵:

$$A_A = \epsilon_{A,RSH}(RSH) + \epsilon_{A,RS^-}(RS^-) \quad (1)$$

$$A_B = \epsilon_{B,RSH}(RSH) + \epsilon_{B,RS^-}(RS^-) \quad (2)$$

In which A_A is the absorbance in the wavelength A, $\epsilon_{A,RSH}$ is the molar absorptivity for the protonated form in the wavelength A, ϵ_{A,RS^-} is the molar absorptivity for the free form in the wavelength A and (RSH) and (RS⁻) are the activities of the protonated and free forms respectively. Similarly are the terms in eq. (2). Such equations are the Lambert-Beer expressions considering that the absorbance is due to the presence of the free and protonated species in each wavelength, made possible to calculate the concentration of acidic and basic forms in equilibrium. The ionic strength is then controlled with an appropriate salt at an appropriate concentration. Using the ratio of these concentrations is possible to calculate the pK_a , according the Handerson-Hasselbach equation (eq. (3)):

$$pK = pH - \log \frac{(RS^-)}{(RSH)} \quad (3)$$

During the calculations the activities of acidic and basic forms are found with the help of eqs. (5) and (6), obtained from the eqs. (2) and (3) system:

$$(RSH) = \frac{[A_A \cdot \epsilon_{B,RS^-}] - [A_B \cdot \epsilon_{A,RS^-}]}{\{\epsilon_{A,RSH} \cdot \epsilon_{B,RS^-} - \epsilon_{A,RS^-} \cdot \epsilon_{B,RSH}\}} \quad (4)$$

$$(RS^-) = \frac{[A_B - \epsilon_{B,RSH} \cdot (RSH)]}{\epsilon_{B,RS^-}} \quad (5)$$

Using the results and the Handerson-Hasselbach equation (eq. (3)), in different pH values, the mean pK_a can be obtained. In Table 2, the pK_a values determined for the cyclic DTC are presented^{35,37,38}. The pyr was the one with lowest pK_a , which suggests that the pyrrolidinedithiocarbamic acid is the strongest acid in the series. These results are in agreement with the intermediate of dithiocarbamates decomposition proposed by Chakrabarty and co-workers¹⁵, according to which the unstable acidic form is present during the decomposition. Although slightly different pK_a values were found using this procedure, the authors showed that the shape of the UV-vis spectra, follows a profile that agrees with the values in Table 1^{35,37,38}, once the presence of two peaks is observed only when the

Table 2. pK_a values determined by spectrophotometric method, using eqs. (4) and (5)

pH	Absorbance		L/HL	pK_a
	$\lambda = 256 \text{ nm}$	$\lambda = 272 \text{ nm}$		
pyr				
2.05	0.7893	1.567	0.07574	3.17
2.49	0.8980	1.568	0.1922	3.21
2.66	1.086	1.633	0.3948	3.06
3.06	1.313	1.606	0.9422	3.08
3.61	1.672	1.607	3.593	3.05
4.47	1.872	1.588	30.16	2.99
			mean	3.10 ± 0.07
pip	$\lambda = 264 \text{ nm}$	$\lambda = 276 \text{ nm}$		
2.05	0.5852	0.9247	0.03015	3.57
2.49	0.6674	0.9773	0.08700	3.55
2.66	0.5102	0.6920	0.1699	3.43
3.06	0.9604	1.191	0.3305	3.54
3.61	1.413	1.490	1.402	3.46
			mean	3.51 ± 0.08
mor	$\lambda = 264 \text{ nm}$	$\lambda = 286 \text{ nm}$		
2.62	0.126	0.134	0.267	3.20
3.25	0.317	0.339	0.341	2.78
3.73	0.463	0.492	0.980	3.74
4.76	0.615	0.643	1.75	4.52
			mean	3.6 ± 0.6
hex	$\lambda = 260 \text{ nm}$	$\lambda = 276 \text{ nm}$		
2.78	0.445	0.713	0.246	3.41
3.39	0.551	0.696	0.854	3.47
4.21	0.735	0.741	3.59	3.65
4.79	0.819	0.778	7.35	3.93
			mean	3.6 ± 0.2

pH of the solution is higher than the values determined in this way.

In this sense, the pK_a order is : pyr < pip < mor < hex

This is probably related with the difficult in the formation of the intermediate in Fig. 1 depending on the histeric hindrance caused by aminic group.

II.3. Decomposition kinetics

The decomposition of pyr, pip, mor, hex, can be followed by the absorbance decay of the peak at 280 nm band at different pH values. The $\ln A/A_0$ vs time plots showed a linear dependence suggesting a pseudo-first order kinetics with slope equal to k_{ap} . Usually a soluble salt as sodium or ammonium is used. The decomposition of dithiocarbamates was investigated by Chakrabarty and co-work-

ers^{15,30-33}. According to these authors the rate of decomposition in basic media is dependent of the pH ($[H^+] \ll K_a$) but in sufficiently acidic solutions ($[H^+] > K_a$) it becomes constant ($k_{ap} = k_{lim}$), according to :

$$k_{ap} = k_{lim} \left(\frac{H^+}{[H^+] + K_a} \right) \quad (4)$$

in which k_{ap} is the apparent rate constant from $\ln A/A_0$ vs time plots, k_{lim} is the limiting rate constant at low pH and K_a is the acidic dissociation constant. The data are summarized in the Table 3 revealing that the stability order :

pyr > hex > pip > mor

This order is probably also related with the DTC structure as discussed above.

Table 3. Kinetic decomposition parameters for the cyclic DTC in different pH, and ionic strength adjusted to 0.50 mol L⁻¹ (NaClO₄)

DTC	k_{lim} (10 ⁻² min ⁻¹)	$\tau_{1/2 \text{ lim}}$ (min)
pyr	2.9 ± 0.2	27 ± 3
pip	4.4 ± 0.4	0.17 ± 0.03
mor	23 ± 7	0.09 ± 0.02
hex	3.68	2.6

III. Thermal behavior and decomposition

In the descriptions presented below, all the intermediates and residues were characterized by X-ray diffraction patterns compared with literature standards, when stable samples could be obtained.

III.1. Ammonium salts

Ammonium salts presented a different behavior depending on the ligand, under N₂ atmosphere. NH₄pyr presented decomposition in a single step according to the TG curves. However the DSC revealed a more complex decomposition that involves : (1) the loss of ammonia with formation of the pyrrolidinedithiocarbamic acid; (2) melting of the acid; (3) decomposition of the liquid phase with release of H₂S³⁷. On the other hand the NH₄pip and NH₄mor presented complete volatilization without melting according both TG and DSC data^{37,38} when the curves are taken at 10 °C min⁻¹. However if the curves are taken at 5 °C min⁻¹ a melting process can be observed in the DSC curves, associated with the volatilization, including for the ammonium diethanolaminedithiocarbamate

(NH₄dedc)²⁷. This fact suggests that a 6-membered ring confers more stability to the compound while the 5-membered ring seems to decompose generating organic matter in the residue.

III.2. RNH₂⁺ salts (RNH = pyrrolidine, piperidine, morpholine, hexamethylenimine and ethanolamine)

The Hpyrpyr and the Hhexhex salts presented melting followed by volatilization. The Hpippip and Hmormor sublimes without melting even at 5 °C min⁻¹ heating rate. The Hdcdcdcd is liquid at room temperature. When the DSC curve is taken starting at -75 °C the onset temperature of the melting is close to 25 °C (peak at 30 °C), followed by a complex decomposition processes from 100-325 °C²⁷.

III.3. Sodium salts

All the sodium salts investigated presented hydration water in their structures and the formulae proposed are : Npyr.2H₂O; Napip.2H₂O; Namor.2.25H₂O; Nahex.2H₂O. Both pyr and pip salts release the water in a single thermal event, while in the mor case, water is lost in two steps respectively with loss of 2 and 0.25 (per mol) and hex releases the 2 water molecules in two consecutive events^{37,39}. The decomposition of sodium pyr and pip salts under nitrogen led to the formation of sodium polysulphide and a carbonaceous residue. Under air, similar observations were possible, but all the residues were characterized as the respective sulphates according to X-ray diffraction patterns^{37,39}.

III.4. Potassium salts

Potassium salts of pyr, pip and mor could be synthesized and thermally analysed under dynamic air atmosphere. They were characterized as Kpyr, Kpip.H₂O and Kmor.H₂O³⁹. The hydrated salts lost water in single step. The anhydrous compounds generated thiosulphates as intermediates of decomposition according to FTIR characterization³⁹, instead of the thiocyanate intermediate described by Sharma³ in his review for other DTC's. The final decomposition products at 800 °C are the potassium sulphates.

III.5. Zinc complexes

Zinc complexes Zn(pyr)₂³⁷, Zn(pip)₂³⁷, Zn(hex)₂²⁹, were analyzed by TG and DSC in which decomposition takes place resulting in ZnS after the decomposition of the complexes which is slowly reduced to Zn⁰ in nitrogen

atmosphere. Under air flow the residues are mixtures of ZnSO₃ + ZnS and ZnSO₄ + ZnO for the pyr and pip complexes respectively. The Zn(hex)₂ resulted in ZnS which was transformed into ZnO. The DSC curves for Zn(pyr)₂³⁷ and Zn(hex)₂²⁹ revealed a phase transition that precedes the melting of the compound while the Zn(pip)₂ melts and then decomposed without that phase transition.

III.6. Cadmium complexes

TG and DTG curves of Cd(pyr)₂³⁷, Cd(pip)₂³⁷, Cd(hex)₂²⁹ showed that under nitrogen all the compounds produced CdS as the final decomposition product. The pyr complex decomposed in two consecutive steps without stable intermediary. Stoichiometric calculations suggested that a thiocyanide may be present according to Sharma proposal. The pip and hex decomposed in a single way. Under air an interesting observation was done once in this case oxysulphates of the type Cd₂OSO₄ are formed as the intermediary of decomposition. These compounds then decomposed to form CdO as final decomposition products^{37,29}. The DSC revealed no evidences for melting in Cd(pyr)₂. However the other two complexes melted before decomposition. No evidences of phase transitions were noted in all the compounds.

III.6. Lead complexes

Cyclic dithiocarbamates Pb(pyr)₂ and Pb(pip)₂³⁷ were prepared and investigated by TG/DTG and DSC. The complexes decomposed in a single step resulting in PbS under nitrogen. The PbS is volatile and some mass loss is observed in the sequence. Intermetallic Pb-Pt can be found when a platinum sample holder is used and submitted to X-ray diffraction analysis after the TG run. Under air all the complexes decomposed in a mixture of PbS and PbSO₄. On further heating the mixture was converted to lead sulphate and a small amount of lead oxysulphate, according to X-ray diffraction data³⁷. DSC curves revealed no evidences of phase transitions in the compounds complexes and that both melted before decomposition.

III.7. Cobalt complexes

The Co(pyr)₂⁴⁰, Co(pip)₂⁴⁰ and Co(mor)₂³⁸ complexes lost water before decomposition. TG/DTG curves of Co(pyr)₂ and Co(pip)₂ showed that under nitrogen atmosphere the compounds produced Co(SCN)₂ as the unstable intermediate followed to polysulphates as residue. However, the Co(mor)₂ decomposed in a single step generating sulphide as residue. Under air atmosphere, the

complexes decomposed in a single step and Co_2O_3 is the main product of thermal decomposition. CoSO_4 , Co_3O_4 , CoO and CoS were detected as decomposition intermediates after oxidation of the organic matter. DSC curves are in total agreement with TG results, showing dehydration represented by broad endothermic process.

III.8. Nickel complexes

$\text{Ni}(\text{pyr})_2$ ⁴⁰, $\text{Ni}(\text{pip})_2$ ⁴⁰, $\text{Ni}(\text{mor})_2$ ³⁸ and $\text{Ni}(\text{hex})_2$ ²⁹ complexes were also obtained. TG/DTG curves revealed that only $\text{Ni}(\text{pip})_2$ lost water of hydration before the decomposition. Under nitrogen atmosphere, the $\text{Ni}(\text{pyr})_2$ complex decomposed via unstable intermediated, probably $\text{Ni}(\text{SCN})_2$, followed by the presence of NiS that is slowly reduced to Ni^0 . The other complexes produced a mixture of Ni and Ni_2S_3 (pip); NiS/Ni (mor); Ni_2S_3 followed by NiS (hex). Under air $\text{Ni}(\text{pyr})_2$ generated NiSO_4 and finally NiO . $\text{Ni}(\text{pip})_2$ generated NiS , NiO/NiSO_4 and then NiO . $\text{Ni}(\text{mor})_2$ decomposed via NiS and then NiO . $\text{Ni}(\text{hex})_2$ produced Ni_2S_3 , that generated Ni_2OSO_4 and finally Ni_2O_3 . The DSC curves agreed with the description of TG curves as above, except for the melting in the $\text{Ni}(\text{hex})_2$.

III.9. Copper complexes

Under nitrogen the copper complexes $\text{Cu}(\text{pyr})_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{pip})_2$ ⁴⁰ losses 2 and 1 hydration water respectively. Both the pyr and hex complex decomposed via thiocyanate, while the pip and mor decomposed in a single step. The final residues were sulphides of the type $\text{CuS}/\text{Cu}_2\text{S}$ (pyr); $\text{Cu}_{1.8}\text{S}$ (pip) and Cu^0 (hex). The $\text{Cu}(\text{mor})_2$ generated Cu_7S_4 after the sequence : $\text{Cu}_{1.8}\text{S} \rightarrow \text{Cu}_{1.92}\text{S} \rightarrow \text{Cu}_7\text{S}_4$. Under air the complexes undergo decomposition after dehydration with formation of $\text{Cu}_2\text{OSO}_4/\text{CuO}/\text{CuSO}_4$ and finally CuSO_4 (pyr); $\text{Cu}_{1.8}\text{S}$ followed by $\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{CuSO}_4$ and finally CuO (pip); CuS/CuO that generates CuO (mor) and $\text{Cu}_2\text{S}(\text{CN})_2 \rightarrow \text{Cu}_2\text{OSO}_4 \rightarrow \text{CuO}$ (hex). According to X-ray diffraction patterns of the residues, being the differences attributed to the different behavior of the organic matter during decomposition. The DSC curves did not show any additional process in relation to the TG/DTG data.

III.10. Silver complexes

TG/DTG curves revealed that under nitrogen atmosphere Agpyr and Agpip ⁴¹ decomposed in a single step generating sulphide, Ag_2S . However, under air atmosphere pip and pyr complexes decomposed via sequence Ag_2S ,

Ag_2SO_4 , Ag . The final product was metallic silver for pyr. The decomposition of pip complex followed the sequence $\text{Ag}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{AgO}$; $\text{Ag}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{Ag}$ generating $\text{Ag}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{Ag}$ mixture as final product. DSC curves are in total agreement with TG/DTG results.

III.11. Iron complexes

Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} complexes of pyr and pip were obtained and their thermal behavior were investigated by TG/DTG and DSC⁴¹. The pyr complexes decomposed slowly without dehydration and the oxygen atom was retained to form Fe_2O_3 as final product in both air and nitrogen atmospheres suggesting that the water molecule is coordinated to the metallic center. Before decomposition the $\text{Fe}(\text{pyr})_3$ presented reduction to $\text{Fe}(\text{pyr})_2$, assisted by the oxidation of the organic matter, since similar TG/DTG and DSC curves were observed in both cases. TG curves of pip complexes under nitrogen atmosphere suggested a sudden one step decomposition process, with different profiles when compared to the pyr analogues. No evidence of reduction was observed for the Fe^{III} complex, since TG/DTG and DSC curves are different from that for $\text{Fe}(\text{pyr})_2$. $\text{Fe}(\text{pip})_2$ decomposed in Fe_2O_3 while $\text{Fe}(\text{pip})_3$ decomposed in FeO/S mixture. Under air the organic part of Fe^{III} and Fe^{II} complexes decomposed faster than in nitrogen. $\text{Fe}(\text{pip})_2$ decomposed in a single step generating Fe_2O_3 and $\text{Fe}(\text{pip})_3$ decomposition follow the sequence Fe_2O_3 ; $\text{Fe}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ and finally Fe_2O_3 .

III.12. Mercury complexes

TG/DTG curves revealed that $\text{Hg}(\text{pyr})_2$ and $\text{Hg}(\text{pip})_2$ ⁴⁰ decomposed in a similar way. The decomposition of the $\text{Hg}(\text{pyr})_2$ residue at 297 °C supports that Hg_2S is present instead of HgS . If mercury(II) sulphide was the residue during the $\text{Hg}(\text{pyr})_2$ decomposition the residue should be stable up to 583 °C, since HgS decomposes only at this temperature⁴². The inflection in the TG curve and DTG peak suggested the formation of thiocyanate as intermediate, in agreement with the residue. When a platinum sample holder is used an amalgam is present and a continuous mass loss until around 800 °C is observed due to its decomposition. The DSC curves showed melting process (pip) and a strong exothermic decomposition that masked the dehydration process.

III.13. Manganese complexes

The $\text{Mn}(\text{pyr})_2$, $\text{Mn}(\text{pip})_2$ ⁴¹ and $\text{Mn}(\text{mor})_2$ ³⁸ complexes

were obtained and investigated by TG/DTG and DSC. Under nitrogen atmosphere $\text{Mn}(\text{pyr})_2$ decomposed in a single step generating MnS , while $\text{Mn}(\text{pip})_2$ presented MnS as decomposition intermediate. The $\text{Mn}(\text{mor})_2$ decomposed via thiocyanate and sulphide as intermediates and Mn^0 as final product of decomposition. $\text{Mn}(\text{pyr})_2$ presented an interesting mass loss before decomposition attributed to sublimation followed by decomposition⁴³. Under air the complexes undergo decomposition after oxidation of the metallic center, with formation of $\text{MnSO}_4/\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_3/\text{MnSO}_4$ and finally $\text{MnSO}_4(\text{pyr})$; MnSO_4 followed by $\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4/\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_3$ and finally $\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4/\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_3/\text{MnO}_2$ (pip); $\text{MnSO}_4/\text{Mn}_x\text{O}_y$ that generates Mn_3O_4 (mor). DSC curves presented the endothermic peak under air for $\text{Mn}(\text{pyr})_2$ that was attributed to solid state structural changes in the complex since there is no mass changes or melting process observed at this temperature. DSC curves of pip and mor complexes suggested that the decomposition occurred in more than one step, via thiocyanate intermediate.

IV. Conclusion

The DTC showed low stability in acidic media. According to Chakrabarti and co-workers, the degradation mechanism in aqueous solution is related with the acidic form represented by an unstable intermediate and generating an amine and carbon disulphide. The instability of the intermediate is due to the positive charge density in the carbon and nitrogen atoms of carbamate bond, which induces the molecule decomposition in acidic media and the formation of such intermediate is related to the structure of aminic group in the DTC. In the series presented here it seems that pyr is the one with more difficulty in forming and stabilizing the intermediate which makes it the more stable in acidic aqueous solution. As a consequence the results of pK_a calculation revealed that pyr was the one with lowest pK_a which pyrrolidinedithiocarbamic acid is the strongest acid in the series :

However the evidences of formation of thiocyanate as degradation intermediates in some cases suggests that the pyr ring breaks, resulting in carbonaceous residues that promotes the reduction of the residue to elemental metal. Similar observations were possible for some hex complexes suggesting the rupture of the 7-membered ring in such cases. Comparing decomposition temperatures of pip and mor complexes one can realize that the presence of the oxygen atom in the amine ring makes the mor derivatives thermally more stable than pip analogues. This should be related with the oxygen tendency to concentrate the electronic density thereby weakening the N-C bond in relation to pip. On the other hand the less tense 5-membered pyr ring results in complexes more stable than the corresponding mor and pip complexes.

Fig. 2. (a) The pyr and Hpyr UV spectra in acid ($\text{pH} = 0.98$) and basic ($\text{pH} = 7.82$) media using diode-array detection. (b) The Lambert-Beer law verification, in the λ_{max} of the acid and basic forms of pyr. The angular coefficients of these curves gave the $\epsilon_{\text{A,RSH}}$, $\epsilon_{\text{B,RSH}}$, $\epsilon_{\text{A,RS}}$, $\epsilon_{\text{B,RS}}$ values.

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